

D5.8 - Use Case V - District heating with Geothermal Technology (Holzkirchen, Germany)

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Summary

This deliverable presents part of the activities and outcomes of Task 5.4 within RESTORE EU project, which focuses on demonstrating the performance and replicability of the RESTORE integrated system in several facilities. The task consists of the implementation, optimization, and validation of six real use-cases through their digital representations, using the RESTORE Simulation Web Platform (IPSE GO). These virtual models aim to replicate real district heating and cooling (DHC) networks across diverse industrial and geographical contexts in Europe, including biomass and solar systems, cement and paper industries, steelworks, geothermal applications, and university campuses.

Deliverable D5.8 deals with the implementation and validation of RESTORE Use-Case V: District heating with Geothermal Technology - Location: Geothermie Holzkirchen Plant, Holzkirchen- Germany.

The information provided in this document builds upon collaboration between TURBODEN, SIMTECH and all RESTORE development partners, in the sense that it considers technical inputs not only from other tasks of WP5, but also from work packages WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4.

The document details the methodological framework used to implement the Use-Case V (related to Sub-task 5.4.5), presenting simulation models for Use-Case V within the RESTORE Virtual Tool, resulting from the integration of the RESTORE concept in DH coupled to the Geothermal Power Plant Facility. For each use-case, the partners defined specific system boundaries, components, and operational conditions, which were then simulated and optimized in the platform. The work provides both a technical validation of the RESTORE concept, economic outcomes assessment and a structured dataset to support environmental impact assessment. Ultimately, the insights gathered here serve as a cornerstone for developing large-scale replication strategies in Task 5.5, facilitating broader deployment of RESTORE technologies across Europe.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	6
2. Holzkirchen Facility.....	7
3. Geothermal Heat Available.....	8
3.1. Heat available on site	8
4. Charging Mode	13
4.1. Heat pump modelling pre-assumptions	13
4.2. Component design and selection	18
4.2.1. Evaporator.....	18
4.2.2. Regenerator	18
4.2.3. Condenser and thermochemical reactor	18
4.2.4. Compressor.....	19
4.3. Heat pump IPSE GO modelling.....	21
4.3.1. Evaporator.....	22
4.3.2. Condenser and thermochemical reactor	23
4.3.3. Compressor.....	24
4.3.4. Heat Pump overall performances	24
4.3.5. Mechanical Vapor Recompression (MVR) integration.....	26
5. Discharging Mode.....	28
6. Conclusions	29
7. References	30

1. Introduction

The RESTORE project introduces an advanced energy recovery system designed to enhance the utilization of low-grade waste heat from industrial processes. WP5 Subtask 5.4.5 (District heating with Geothermal Technology) addresses the implementation and virtual replication of the RESTORE TCES concept within the Holzkirchen geothermal plant for the implementation of Use Case V.

The site selected for Case Study V is the geothermal power plant located in Holzkirchen, Bavaria. This facility features an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) system supplied by Turboden, with an installed electrical capacity of 3.6 MW.

The aim of this study is to optimize the use of available geothermal heat to ensure a more stable thermal energy withdrawal throughout the year, thereby maximizing the productivity of the geothermal well and better matching the thermal demand profile of the end user. To achieve this, the integration of a thermochemical energy storage system powered by a heat pump is explored. This system would upgrade heat from medium- and low-temperature sources (which is the output brine outside the ORC, in summer) to a level of temperature suitable for district heating.

This approach aims to enhance both the direct utilization of thermal energy and the indirect improvement of electrical generation, contributing to a more efficient and sustainable operation of the geothermal plant.

General information about the Use-Case V and its geothermal power plant located in Holzkirchen, Bavaria in Germany, is described in the public documentation of “RESTORE Use-Cases Modelling” concerning WP5 Task T5.4: Implementation, optimization, management & validation of the six RESTORE Use-Cases, which is available in the project’s Zenodo Community account <https://zenodo.org/communities/101036766/records>).

2. Holzkirchen Facility

The site selected for Use-Case V is the geothermal power plant located in Holzkirchen, Bavaria, Germany. This facility is equipped with an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) system supplied by Turboden, designed to convert geothermal heat into electricity and thermal energy. The plant has an installed electrical capacity of 3.6 MW and extracts geothermal fluid from a depth of approximately 4800 meters, with reservoir temperatures around 140 °C.

The existing ORC system operates with a closed-loop cycle using an organic working fluid, which is vaporized by geothermal heat and expanded in a turbine to generate electricity. After expansion, the fluid is condensed and recirculated. The system is characterized by high operational flexibility, with part-load operation ranging from 10% to 110% of nominal capacity and an average availability exceeding 98%.

The objective of Use-Case V is to optimize the use of available geothermal heat to ensure a more constant thermal energy withdrawal throughout the year. This approach aims to maximize the productivity of the geothermal well while better aligning with the thermal demand profile of the end user. This work will analyze the current configuration and explore strategies to enhance thermal utilization without compromising system stability or reservoir sustainability.

Figure 1 Holzkirchen Geothermal Power Plant

3. Geothermal Heat Available

The geothermal power plant under consideration features thermal energy extraction system, which provides access to three distinct temperature levels: a high-temperature stream at approximately 140 °C used to power the existing Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) unit for electricity generation and for the District Heating and a mid and low-temperature stream at approximately 60 °C and 14 °C.

The focus of this study is both the indirect enhancement of electrical generation, and the direct improvement of the utilization of the available thermal energy. Specifically, the objective is to investigate the integration of a thermochemical energy storage system, fed by a heat pump, capable of upgrading heat from the medium and low-temperature sources to a temperature level suitable for district heating. The medium source is the residual heat available after the ORC power plant use.

3.1. Heat available on site

As mentioned, in the geothermal power plant of Use-Case V, there are three different heat profiles on site. The ones which are interesting for the Heat Pump feeding the Reactor are the 14 °C (low temperature resource) and the 60 °C (middle temperature resource) resources, therefore a study on both these resources was conducted.

The low temperature (approximately 14 °C) represents residual thermal energy that is typically underutilized.

The objective of this virtual use-case implementation, is to explore the integration of a thermochemical energy storage system, supported by a heat pump, capable of upgrading heat from the medium- and low-temperature sources. The goal is to store thermal energy at a temperature sufficiently high to be compatible with district heating requirements.

The available flow rate of this low temperature heat source is not available since there is no flow meter installed, we can imagine to have approximately 100 kg/s to feed the evaporator of the Heat Pump.

The medium temperature resource could come from the ORC thermal water outlet temperature. The flowrate is constant, as typically for geothermal plants, at around 95 kg/s.

District Heating Demand: Seasonal Comparison

The time series graphs illustrate the variation in thermal power demand for district heating across different months.

In January, the average thermal power demand was approximately 2 MW, with daily fluctuations likely driven by external temperature changes and user behavior.

This level of demand reflects typical winter conditions, where heating requirements are consistently high.

In contrast, during June, the average thermal power demand dropped significantly, stabilizing around a fraction of a MegaWatt.

This reduction corresponds to the seasonal decrease in heating needs. By July, the demand nearly vanished, indicating minimal or no requirement for space heating, possibly limited to domestic hot water supply or residual system loads.

This seasonal variability highlights the challenge of maintaining a stable geothermal heat extraction rate throughout the year.

Figures 2 and 3 present the distribution of the District Heating Thermal Power in the months of January and June of 2025.

Figure 2 District Heating Thermal Power in January 2025

Figure 3 District Heating Thermal Power in June 2025

The district heating system currently utilizes a fraction of the geothermal water that is at a temperature sufficiently high for electricity generation. From an exergetic perspective, this represents a sub-optimal use of the resource, as high-grade thermal energy is being diverted to low-exergy applications.

To address this point, a seasonal strategy is proposed. During the summer months, when district heating demand is minimal and surplus renewable electricity is typically available on the grid, the thermochemical reactor can be charged using the residual heat from the ORC system, without extracting additional geothermal fluid. This allows for efficient energy storage without impacting the geothermal reservoir.

In winter, the stored thermal energy can be discharged to support the district heating network. This enables the full thermal output of the geothermal wells to be directed toward the ORC system, maximizing electricity generation at a time when renewable electricity availability is generally lower.

This approach improves the overall exergy efficiency of the system and enhances seasonal flexibility in energy management.

ORC Power Output: Seasonal Comparison

The time series graphs show the variation in electrical power output from the Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) system during different months. In January, the power output is noticeably lower than in June, despite the colder ambient temperatures, which would typically favor higher ORC efficiency due to improved heat rejection conditions.

This counterintuitive trend is explained by the operational strategy of the geothermal plant: in winter, a significant portion of the high-temperature geothermal fluid is diverted to supply the district heating network. As a result, less thermal energy is available for the ORC system, leading to reduced electricity generation.

In June, when district heating demand is minimal, the ORC system receives a larger share of the geothermal heat, allowing it to operate closer to its nominal capacity. This results in higher electrical output, even though ambient conditions are less favorable for thermodynamic efficiency.

Figures 4 and 5 present (in red) the distribution of gross electrical power produced in the months of January and June of 2025.

Figure 4 In red - gross electrical power produced in January 2025

Figure 5 In red – gross electrical power produced in June 2025

The observed reduction in ORC power output during winter, despite favorable ambient conditions, is primarily due to the diversion of geothermal heat toward district heating. This limits the thermal energy available for electricity generation, resulting in lower electrical output when renewable electricity from other sources is also scarce.

To address this, a strategic use of heat pumps during the summer months is proposed. When surplus renewable electricity is available on the grid, particularly from solar sources, the heat pump can be used to charge the thermochemical reactor using residual heat from the ORC system, without additional geothermal extraction. This stored thermal energy can then be discharged in winter to support the district heating network, allowing the entire geothermal thermal output to be directed to the ORC system for maximized electricity production.

This approach not only improves the exergy efficiency of the system but also enhances its seasonal flexibility, aligning energy production with grid conditions and thermal demand.

4. Charging Mode

This chapter outlines the design and operational concept of the Large Heat Pump (LHP) system to be implemented within the scope of the RESTORE project. The system has been developed based on the technical requirements provided and Turboden's experience in delivering similar industrial solutions.

Key features of the system include:

- **Application:** Waste heat recovery for the charging phase of a thermochemical energy storage (TCES) reactor
- **Working fluid:** Cyclopentane
- **Heat sink interface:** Thermochemical reactor
- **Heat source:** Hot water from an industrial process

The LHP is designed to transfer thermal energy from the industrial process to the TCES reactor when waste heat is available, and electricity prices are favorable. The stored thermal energy can later be used as a high-temperature source for an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) to generate electricity when needed.

The LHP operates by transferring heat from a cold source (heat source) to a hot sink using a compressor driven by an electric motor. It activates when heat generation is requested and the cold source is available, with control signals managed via an external interface. The system automatically adjusts its thermal output to match the demand from the heat sink loop. In response to variations in the heat source (temperature and flow rate), the LHP modulates its load to maintain a stable setpoint. All operational adjustments are handled by the integrated process control system, ensuring reliable and efficient performance.

4.1. Heat pump modelling pre-assumptions

Starting from heat source data, given by the customer, a study followed by an optimization process on the choice of components, configuration and fluid has been carried out and will be detailed in the following chapter.

The Large Heat Pump (LHP) system is schematically represented in the conceptual process diagram below. From a thermodynamic standpoint, the system operates by utilizing a heat source to evaporate the working fluid (WF) at low pressure within the evaporator. Once the WF has been evaporated it can be superheated entering the regenerator before entering the compressor. The compressor, using electricity, is able to increase the temperature and pressure of the fluid that will condense inside the condenser releasing heat to the heat sink (in this case the stream entering the TCES reactor).

Figure 6 LHP concept scheme for Use-Case V

All the scheme and analysis reported in this chapter have been performed before starting the IPSE GO usage, in order to have some general arrangement to start the modelling work.

The system includes the following key components:

- **Evaporator:** Enables the working fluid to absorb thermal energy from an external heat source, initiating the evaporation process.
- **Regenerator:** Recovers residual heat from within the circuit, thereby improving the overall efficiency of the LHP system. It is also used to superheat the working fluid before entering the compressor to avoid that any unevaporated liquid droplets will impact the compressor impeller. This heat exchanger was not considered in this study as result of the optimization study. The reason will be assessed later on.
- **Centrifugal compressor:** Its purpose is to increase the WF pressure and temperature. It is composed of three impellers mounted in two casings on a common gearbox.
- **Condenser:** Serves as the main interface with the thermochemical reactor, allowing the working fluid to release heat and undergo condensation.
- **Expansion valve:** Decreases the pressure of the working fluid to the minimum level required to “close” the thermodynamic cycle.

The modelling and simulation of this complex thermodynamic cycle were made possible thanks to the IPSEGO platform that is able to provide a flexible and powerful environment for

designing and analyzing the LHP system, allowing for detailed representation of each component and their interactions.

Figure 7 $T-Q$ diagram of the process

The LHP process is based on a thermodynamic cycle reported in Figure 7 above. It includes the following main transformations (the reference number for the transformations is presented in the scheme of Figure 7):

- Evaporation of the WF at constant low pressure and temperature in the evaporator (5-1)
- Compression of the WF inside the compressor (1-2)
- Condensation of the WF at constant high pressure and temperature inside the condenser (2-3)
- Subcooling of the WF (3-4)
- Expansion of the WF through a dedicated expansion valve (4-5)

After conducting some rounds of modeling and simulation, the decision to adopt the current configuration of the Large Heat Pump (LHP) system was driven by the objective of maximizing

the overall efficiency of the machine also considering possible cost savings. Various alternative layouts were initially considered, each with different component arrangements and thermodynamic strategies. However, through iterative analysis and performance comparison, it became evident that the selected scheme offered the best balance between energy recovery, pressure management, and thermal exchange.

Ultimately, the chosen scheme—without regenerator, dual-stage compression, and strategic pressure management via expansion valves—proved to be the most effective in enhancing the system's coefficient of performance (COP).

As first simulation a cycle with a lower source temperature was carried out. Since the temperature profile of the source was 14-10°C, n-butane was selected as WF. Such lower temperature influences the WF compressor suction pressure. The lower is the evaporating temperature the lower will be the pressure of the WF entering the compressor thus, the compressor, to guarantee the same outlet sink temperature, have to consume more electrical power. This greatly affects the performance (COP) that are measured with the ratio of the useful heat on consumed electric power.

Since the client confirmed that a higher temperature stream was available the choice switched on a new configuration.

For this temperature range 59-55°C cyclopentane resulted to be more efficient under a thermodynamic point of view with respect to n-butane. This, together with the higher evaporating temperature allow to reduce the electrical consumption up to around 47%. This led to an increase of the COP of the same figure (considering a constant output thermal power).

In the analysis, it has been shown that the “classic configuration” composed of evaporator, regenerator, condenser and sub-cooler as heat exchangers could have a possible improvement. From the simulation it results that the regenerator was exchanging a very low thermal energy. This is due to the high subcooling that is occurring in the sub-cooler. For this reason, a configuration without the regenerator has been proposed. This final configuration reflects what is represented in figure 5.

The problem that can arise from the removal of the regenerator like the possible condensation of the vapor WF before entering the compressor can be overcome by handling the superheating degree of the vapor inside the evaporator and foreseen inside the Kettle enough space in the shell to avoid any dragging of possible liquid. In addition, a demister can be used at the outlet of the evaporator. This will remove possible liquid particle that can be dragged/entrain the vapor that is going out the evaporator.

This is something that is already done in a similar Turboden LHP plant that is under operation. Figure 8 illustrates a representation of the aforementioned plant also working without regenerator.

Figure 8 Turboden LHP Plant

Some advantages deriving from this choice impacts:

- Cost: there is a lower amount of heat exchanger
- Footprint: not having a regenerator, that should lie below the condenser level, will reduce the overall height of the plant
- Performance: In this case, since the regenerator was exchanging a small amount of heat there was no appreciable advantage in the performance. Removing this equipment made the overall efficiency (COP) increase. This is because the pressure at the compressor suction resulted slightly higher than in the case of employing the regenerator (that have some pressure losses that need to be account)

After evaluating several working fluids, cyclopentane was selected due to its higher “affinity” to the temperature level of the heat source, superior performance in terms of COP, easier plant layout, and compatibility with both compression and expansion (ORC) cycles. Its high condensation temperature and low Global Warming Potential (GWP = 5) make it an efficient and environmentally responsible choice. Using the same fluid for both charging and discharging phases also simplifies system design, allowing for a single storage tank and streamlined fluid management.

The optimization process and the step to define the final configuration before the modeling with IPSEGO are summarized as follow:

- Definition of available heat source, interfacing with client
- Selection of the working fluid based on input and required output. This fluid must be suitable for the specific conditions and requirements of the cycle to ensure optimal performance.
- Thermodynamic Cycle Calculations: detailed calculations are performed to define the thermodynamic cycle. These calculations help in understanding the energy transformations and efficiencies within the cycle. This allows to define components, and figures of efficiencies.
- Heat Exchange Calculations: Following the cycle definition, calculations related to heat exchange are carried out. These calculations are crucial for determining how heat is transferred within the system and ensuring effective thermal management. This also gives actual indication on pressure losses and performance of the item other than give mechanical detail of the component.
- Compressor design: Thermodynamic simulations are the basis to perform the design of the compressor technology to be used in the plant. This is the core activity to determine the feasibility of all the LHP plant. Compressor is the core item of an heat pump and the choice directly impacts the overall efficiency.

These steps collectively contribute to the optimization of a thermodynamic cycle, enhancing efficiency and performance while ensuring the system operates effectively under the given conditions.

4.2. Component design and selection

In this chapter the design and the selection of the component models, for the simulation of Use-Case V, are described.

4.2.1. Evaporator

The evaporator is responsible for transferring thermal energy from the heat source to the working fluid (WF), which vaporizes during the process. It is designed as a shell-and-tube heat exchanger, where the heat source flows through the tube side, and the working fluid circulates on the shell side. This configuration ensures efficient heat transfer due to the large surface area provided by the tubes and allows for better control of phase change dynamics.

The shell-side arrangement is particularly advantageous for handling phase transitions, as it accommodates the volume expansion of the vaporizing fluid and facilitates uniform distribution. Additionally, the design supports maintenance and scalability, making it suitable for high-performance applications like the Large Heat Pump system.

Once the thermodynamic requirements for the heat exchanger were defined, the design phase of the shell-and-tube evaporator was initiated. This involved specifying the geometric configuration, material selection, and flow arrangements to ensure optimal heat transfer performance and compatibility with the working fluid and operating conditions of the system.

4.2.2. Regenerator

The Regenerator task is to transfer heat from the saturated liquid coming from the condensation process to the WF vapor coming from the Evaporator.

Through this step the liquid is sub-cooled and the fluid expansion inside the valve is improved by reducing the fraction of liquid that vaporize during the expansion. In this use-case, this step is not foreseen, due to the previously mentioned reasons.

4.2.3. Condenser and thermochemical reactor

The condenser task is to transfer heat from the WF that condensate during the process to the heat sink (the Thermochemical reactor) It is a shell & tube once-through type heat exchanger with the heat sink on tube side and WF on shell side.

All the reactions previously presented in the deliverables that operate within the compatible temperature range can be considered suitable for integration into the system. In this context, a specific reaction has been proposed: the use of a continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) containing $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ suspended in thermal oil, as introduced in the RESTORE project, proposed by Wedl et al., 2024 [9].

Copper sulfate pentahydrate is a promising thermochemical material for medium-temperature energy storage due to its ability to undergo reversible hydration and dehydration reactions, enabling efficient heat storage and release. The reaction proceeds through successive dehydration steps—from pentahydrate to trihydrate, then to monohydrate, and finally to anhydrous CuSO_4 —each occurring at progressively higher temperatures. This stepwise behavior allows for gradual and controllable thermal energy management, making it well-suited for integration with industrial heat sources.

4.2.4. Compressor

The compressor selection process was the result of an iterative exchange between the thermodynamic cycle design and the turbomachinery engineering team at Turboden. This approach allowed for refinement of both the cycle parameters and the machine specifications.

The compressor is the core item of the plant and the most important item to control. The compressor used in the LHP is a centrifugal type with integral gear configuration developed by Turboden. The compressor is specifically designed for the use with heavy molecular weight fluids (like cyclopentane), and it is characterized by the semi-hermetic configuration with minimal leakage of working fluid toward the atmosphere.

The required overall compressor is given by an integrally geared compressor, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Turboden Compressor

COMPRESSOR

Manufacturer	Turboden S.p.A.
Compressor model	Turboden HIT 30
Type of compressor	Integrally Geared – compound type
Impeller type	Design on purpose
Number compressors	One (1)
Casing type	Standardized
Casing connection to gearbox	HIRTH coupling

Shaft end seal type	Mechanical seal
<u>GEARBOX</u>	
Gear unit type	patented

Figure 10 Details of the Turboden Compressor HIT 30

Below, a table containing the main results of the compressor unit simulated in the phase before the IPSEGO simulation, is presented.

CM1	Fluido	-	Cyclopentane
	N° Compressor	-	1
	P_{in}	bar	0,902
	T_{in}	°C	52,81
	V_{in}	m ³ /s	1,847
	SS_{in}	m/s	201,232
	P_{out}	bar	2,000
	T_{out}	°C	81,64
	V_{out}	m ³ /s	0,886
	SS_{out}	m/s	204,733
	P_{mecc}	kW	185
	ΔH_{iso}	kJ/kg	31,0
	β_{vol}	-	2,08
	β_{pres}	-	2,22
	η_{mecc}	-	92,21%
η_{iso}	-	82,0%	

CM2	Fluido	-	Cyclopentane
	N° Compressor	-	1
	P_{in}	bar	1,945
	T_{in}	°C	81,54
	V_{in}	m ³ /s	0,912
	SS_{in}	m/s	204,965
	P_{out}	bar	3,763
	T_{out}	°C	106,48
	V_{out}	m ³ /s	0,488
	SS_{out}	m/s	205,105
	P_{mecc}	kW	167
	ΔH_{iso}	kJ/kg	26,9
	β_{vol}	-	1,87
	β_{pres}	-	1,93
	η_{mecc}	-	92,21%
η_{iso}	-	79,0%	

4.3. Heat pump IPSE GO modelling

The selected case of operation, as mentioned in the previous paragraph, is the one which exploits the 59°C resource.

Figure 11 presents the overall model of Use-Case V modelled within IPSE GO.

UC5 Holzkirchen
Heat Pump for TCES Charging and Direct Discharging for District Heat

Geothermal water is used as heat source for charging the thermochemical energy storage (TCES) via a heat pump (HP).
When the stored thermochemical material is discharged, it is directly used to provide district heat.

Figure 11 IPSE GO Use-Case V Model

4.3.1. Evaporator

The evaporator is a shell and tube heat exchanger with working fluid on shell side.

Figure 12 Evaporator modelling details

Item	Input Value	Calculated Result
S Type defines the type of heat exchanger	counter_current	
S Calculate_profile select if the internal profile calculation shall be done or not	Yes	
P nSlices number of slices used in the external profile calculation functions	10	10
P delta_p_hot pressure drop of the high temperature side	0,6 bar	0,6 bar
P delta_p_cold pressure drop of the low temperature side	0,1 bar	0,1 bar
P heat_loss percentage of heat lost to the surroundings	0 %	0 %
X dt_in temperature difference at the inlet of the low temperature side	3,84713 °C	3,85 °C
X dt_out temperature difference at the outlet of the low temperature side	6,01 °C	6,01 °C
X dt_min minimum (pinch) temperature difference	3,85367 °C	3,85 °C
X PinchPosition position in htex where minimum temperature difference occurs	1,8626e-10	1,8626e-10
X htc_area heat transfer coefficient x transfer area	295,186 kW/K	241,69 kW/K
<input type="button" value="Load Defaults"/> <input type="button" value="Import Estimates"/> <input type="button" value="OK"/> <input type="button" value="Cancel"/>		

Figure 13 Evaporator starting input values represented in IPSE GO

4.3.2. Condenser and thermochemical reactor

Figure 14 Block Condenser - Thermochemical Reactor modelled in IPSE GO

Item	Input Value	Calculated Result
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> delta_p pressure drop in the reactor	0 bar	0 bar
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> conv_TCM conversion fraction of TCM	0,95 kg/kg	0,95 kg/kg
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> t_reac temperature of the reaction	106 °C	106 °C
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> q_trans transferred heat	1920 kW	2115,6 kW
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> q_reac heat consumed by the reaction	1637,83 kW	1839,66 kW
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> q_preheat heat required to bring all incoming streams to reaction temperature	282,166 kW	275,93 kW
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> delta_H_reac heat reaction of dehydration of TCM	923,207 kJ/kg	919,7 kJ/kg
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> hWater water enthalpy at reaction temperature	2583,21 kJ/kg	2583,21 kJ/kg
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> molarmass_Material1 molar mass of TCM 1	249,685 kg/kmol	249,69 kg/kmol
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> molarmass_Material2 molar mass of TCM 2	177,624 kg/kmol	177,62 kg/kmol
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> H_298_15_Material1 enthalpy of formation of TCM1	-2276,51 kJ/kg	-2276,51 kJ/kg
<input type="checkbox"/> H_298_15_Material2		

Figure 15 IPSE GO Condenser Modelling Details

4.3.3. Compressor

Figure 16 IPSE GO Compressor Model used in Use-Case V

During the implementation of the energy system within the simulation software, it was necessary to increase the Heat Pump discharge temperature in order to properly match the thermal requirements of the thermochemical reactor.

This adjustment was essential to ensure compatibility with the operating conditions of the reactor during the charging phase.

As a result, the entire Heat Pump cycle had to be redesigned and re-modeled using IPSE GO.

The new configuration accounts for the altered heat rejection profile and ensures that the system can operate efficiently under the new boundary conditions.

The compressor characteristics are taken from Turboden library.

4.3.4. Heat Pump overall performances

The working fluid quantity calculation is defined considering the most demanding condition between operation and start up based on performances defined by the Customer.

After a first draft of the main component the preliminary fluid quantity esteem is around 2.000 kg.

Hereafter, we present the performance values for the Heat pump, as shown on the IPSE GO platform.

HP Charging	value	unit
Cycle El. Power Input	531.54	[kW]
Condenser Heat to Reactor	2115.5	[kW]
Evaporator Heat Transfer	1600	[kW]
COP	3.98	[-]
Compressor Pressure Ratio	5.87	[-]
Compressor Mass Flow	5.93	[kg/s]
Compressor Inlet Volumetric Flow	2464.93	[l/s]
Compressor Outlet Volumetric Flow	465.79	[l/s]
Condenser U*A	343.52	[kW/K]
Evaporator U*A	241.69	[kW/K]

- Equivalent operation hours (charging): The system operated for a total of 3,000 hours in charging mode, indicating a substantial period of active energy storage throughout the year.
- TCM produced: A total of 26,870 tonnes of thermochemical material (TCM) can be processed.
- TCES steam heat produced: The system delivered 4,632,340 kWh of usable steam heat.

The steam produced by the thermochemical energy storage (TCES) system offers multiple potential applications, depending on the temperature level, pressure, and integration strategy. Three main utilization pathways have been identified:

1. **Direct Connection to District Heating Network:** The steam can be directly fed into the district heating line, particularly to serve users requiring domestic hot water. The power level and temperature are compatible with typical residential or commercial heating needs, making this a straightforward and effective use of the stored thermal energy even during summer.
2. **Internal Recirculation via Heat Pump:** Another option is to recirculate the steam internally within the heat pump system to improve its coefficient of performance (COP) or to support auxiliary heating stages. However, in large-scale installations such as this

one, this approach introduces significant complexity in terms of control, piping, and thermal balancing. The added engineering and operational challenges make this solution less attractive from both a technical and economic standpoint.

3. **Feed Source for Mechanical Vapor Recompression (MVR):** A more advanced application involves using the TCES steam as a thermal input for a Mechanical Vapor Recompression (MVR) system. The MVR compressor increases the enthalpy of the steam, making it suitable for industrial processes such as those in the pharmaceutical or food sectors, where high-grade steam is required. A selection of a suitable vapor compressor has been carried out to evaluate this integration, considering pressure ratios, flow rates, and energy consumption.

This last possibility (3) is investigated more deeply in the next paragraph.

4.3.5. Mechanical Vapor Recompression (MVR) integration

To enhance the value and versatility of the steam produced by the thermochemical energy storage (TCES) system, a Mechanical Vapor Recompression (MVR) unit has been selected and configured. This technology allows the enthalpy of low-pressure steam to be increased through mechanical compression, making it suitable for high-grade industrial applications.

Figure 17 Heater details

System Configuration

The setup consists of two MVR units, each with two compression stages, operating in series.

- Steam input conditions:
 - Mass flow rate: 0.6 kg/s
 - Temperature: 100 °C
 - Pressure: 1 bar
- Steam output conditions:
 - Mass flow rate: 0.73 kg/s (increased due to inter-stage attemperation using diverted cooling water or source water)
 - Temperature: 190 °C
 - Pressure: 10 bar
- Performance Metrics

Electrical consumption: 510 kW, representing the mechanical energy required for compression.

- Useful thermal effect: The output steam, at 10 bar and $\sim 180^{\circ}\text{C}$, is suitable for direct industrial use. Considering the condensation of this steam as the useful effect, the system achieves a Coefficient of Performance (COP) of 2.91, indicating efficient energy conversion.
- Industrial Applications

This high-grade steam can be used in various sectors, including:

- Pharmaceutical manufacturing
- Food processing
- Industrial laundries
- Any process requiring saturated or superheated steam

The modular nature of the MVR system, as illustrated in Figure 18, allows for scalability: additional compression stages can be added to reach even higher pressure and temperature levels, depending on specific process requirements.

Figure 18 Example of MVR application

This integration offers a promising pathway to valorize the stored thermal energy from TCES, especially when direct district heating use is not optimal or when industrial steam demand is present nearby.

5. Discharging Mode

The discharge phase of the thermochemical reactor is designed to deliver thermal energy directly to the district heating network, without intermediate conversion stages. This integration is made possible by the reactor's ability to release heat at temperature and pressure levels compatible with district heating requirements, in this case 85°C with a temperature drop in the heat exchanger of 10°C.

Figure 19 Discharging mode of Use-Case V on IPSE GO

Discharging (Use-Case V)	value	unit
duration discharging	358	hour
TCM consumed	26870	t
Heat produced	758212	kWh

6. Conclusions

The RESTORE solution proposed and adapted to Use-Case V has been thoroughly described in this document. This deliverable presents the design, simulation, and performance evaluation of the TCES (Thermo-Chemical Energy Storage) configuration integrated in a geothermal plant, developed by TURBODEN with support from SIMTECH.

Thanks to the integration of the thermochemical reactor, the system can support the district heating network for approximately 358 hours per year, allowing the entire geothermal thermal output to be directed to the ORC. This results in an estimated increase of 500 kW in electrical output during this period.

- Additional electricity produced annually: 179,000 kWh
- Equivalent CO₂ savings: 71.6 tonnes of CO₂ per year
(Based on a grid emission factor of 0.4 kg CO₂/kWh)

In summary, the above results demonstrate the environmental and energetic benefit of decoupling heat supply from geothermal extraction during peak heating demand, while enhancing the electrical output when renewable electricity is less available.

Overall, the findings presented in this report reinforce the suitability of the integration of the RESTORE proposed solution to District heating with Geothermal Technology, as virtually demonstrated in Use-Case V.

7. References

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